

EXPERIMENTS TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF ISO-FENCHONE. PART I. A SYNTHESIS OF $\beta\delta$ -DIMETHYLPENTANE- $\beta\delta\epsilon$ -TRICARBOXYLIC ACID.*

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Bertraum and Helle (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1900, *ii*, 61, 293) found that the hydration of *l*- α -fenchene with sulphuric—acetic acid mixture gave rise to *iso*-fenchyl alcohol, different from fenchyl alcohol. On oxidation with chromic acid, the new alcohol yielded *isofenchone* (I). The subsequent degradation experiments of Wallach (*Annalen*, 1907, 357, 49; 1908, 363, 1; 1909, 369, 97) and more notably of Aschan (*Annalen*, 1912, 387, 1) and Tiovonon (*ibid.*, 1919, 419, 176) on the ketone brought to light a series of interesting compounds amongst which *isofenchocamphoric acid* (II) and *isofenchocamphononic acid* (III) may be mentioned. Although very careful degradation work has established the structures (I), (II) and (III), no synthetic evidence, however, has been adduced for any of them and the need for work in this direction becomes obvious. In the present paper is recorded the synthesis of $\beta\delta$ -dimethylpentane- $\beta\delta\epsilon$ -tricarboxylic acid (VI, R=H). *iso*Fenchocamphononic acid (III) too was synthesised starting from (II) but in this the author has been anticipated by Bardhan and Ganguly (*J. Chem Soc.*, 1936, 1852) and detailed description is, therefore, not made of this part of the work.

Ruzicka's method (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1367) in his classical synthesis of fenchone was adopted for the present synthesis. Ethyl mesitonate (ethyl α -dimethylacrylate) (IV) (Pinner, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 579; cf. Anschutz and Gillet, *Annalen*, 1888, 287, 99) condensed with zinc and ethyl bromoacetate to yield the lactone of ethyl β -hydroxy- $\beta\delta\delta$ -trimethyladipate (V). The lactonic ester added potassium cyanide at 220°, and hydrolysis of the nitrile and simultaneous esterification (cf. Ruzicka, *loc.cit.*) yielded ethyl $\beta\delta$ -dimethylpentane- $\beta\delta\epsilon$ -tricarboxylate (VI, R=Et). The conversion of this

* A short preliminary note about this work appeared in *Current Science* (1936, 8, 190).

to (III) was accomplished by cyclising it with sodium in benzene to (VII) and hydrolysing and decarboxylating the latter.

(IV)

Experiments are in progress towards the preparation of (III) in quantity with a view to utilising it for the synthesis of *isofenchone* (I) and *isofenchochamic acid* (II).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mesitonic Acid.—Pinner's method (*Ber.*, 1881, 41, 1072) was adopted. The process was tedious and the yield was poor (10-14 g. from 100 g. of acetone).

Ethyl Mesitonate (IV).—The following procedure gave a good yield of the substance. Mesitonic acid (69 g.) was mixed with absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (1.5 c.c.) and alcohol vapour from boiling alcohol (460 c.c.) was bubbled through the mixture for 1½ hours. After cooling, water was added, the ester layer taken up in ether, the ethereal solution dried and ether removed. Ethyl mesitonate was collected at 108-10°/25mm. (112-115°/28mm.), yield 70 g.

The *Semicarbazone* separated from an aqueous alcoholic solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride, sodium acetate and the ester. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 154°. It is soluble in commoner organic solvents and in boiling water. (Found: N, 18.63. C₁₀H₁₉O₃N₃ requires N, 18.36 per cent).

The *2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared following the details of Allen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2950). It crystallised from alcohol in which it was sparingly soluble in slender orange needles, m.p. 98°; easily soluble in acetone and chloroform. (Found: N, 16.13. C₁₃H₂₀O₆N₄ requires N, 15.92 per cent).

Lactone of Ethyl β-Hydroxy-β,β,β-trimethyl adipate (V).—Ethyl mesitonate (64.5 g.) was dissolved in benzene (200 c.c.) and zinc wool ("Reformatsky,"

25 g.) was added. Ethyl bromoacetate (30 g.) was then added and the mixture heated on the water-bath ($\frac{1}{2}$ hour) when the exothermic reaction started. The reaction was maintained by the gradual addition of the remaining bromo-ester (33 g.) and when the addition was over, the flask was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour more to complete the reaction. After cooling the contents were treated with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer separated, washed successively with dilute sulphuric acid, dilute ammonia and water, dried and benzene removed. The benzene residue yielded after repeated fractionation the lactonic ester as a thin, colourless liquid, b.p. $137-38^{\circ}/6$ mm. ($122^{\circ}/1-2$ mm.), yield 30 g. A high boiling fraction, $180^{\circ}/3-4$ mm. was also obtained (*cf.* Ruzicka, *loc. cit.*). The lactonic ester was insoluble in dilute sodium carbonate solution but dissolved slowly in $N/10$ -alkali. From the solution, the silver salt could be precipitated. (Found: C, 61.76; H, 8.83. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.67; H, 8.41 per cent). d_{20}^{25} , 1.0648; n_D^{25} , 1.4430.

Lactone of β -Hydroxy- $\beta\delta\delta$ -trimethyladipic Acid.—The ester (5 g.) was boiled for 1 hour with caustic potash (4 g.) in alcohol (35 c.c., 80 %), the solution was evaporated after addition of water, the residue extracted with ether and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The lactonic acid separated as an oil which solidified immediately. It was recrystallised from water in prisms, m.p. $128-29^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 57.7; H, 7.9. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.0; H, 7.5 per cent).

Action of KCN on the Lactonic Ester: $\beta\delta$ -Dimethylpentane- $\beta\delta\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid and its Ethyl ester (VI).—The above lactonic ester (28 g.) was mixed with finely powdered potassium cyanide (12.8 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux on a paraffin-bath at 220° for 10 hours. The brownish black semi-solid mass was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) and refluxed for 10 hours on an oil-bath. The product was evaporated cautiously and the residue exhaustively extracted with ether (12 times), the ethereal solution dried and the ether removed. The residue (18.2 g.) solidified in part. For obtaining the tricarboxylic acid, the crude product (2 g.) was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and extracted with ether to remove any neutral impurities. Reacidification and extraction with ether and removal of ether gave a product which solidified partly. This was triturated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and filtered. The solid acid melted at 172° . *$\beta\delta$ -Dimethylpentane- $\beta\delta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (VI, R=H)* melted after two recrystallisations from dilute hydrochloric acid (plates) at $185-86^{\circ}$, the m.p. not rising with further crystallisations. (Found: C, 51.75; H, 7.2. Equiv., 77.75. $C_{10}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 51.72; H, 6.9 per cent. $\bar{E}$ quiv., 77.3).

The above method of hydrolysis was not satisfactory, very small yield of the tricarboxylic ester being obtained on esterifying the crude product. Some unreacted lactonic ester was recovered. Ruzicka's method (*loc. cit.*) was found to be better. To the crude product of reaction obtained from the lactonic ester (20 g.) and potassium cyanide (9.3 g.), absolute alcohol (65 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (35 g.) were added and the mixture heated for 9 days under gentle reflux on an oil-bath. The product obtained was poured into water and the oily layer extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried and ether removed. The brownish residue was distilled in vacuum when a main fraction, b.p. 165-170°/7-8 mm. (9.3 g.) was obtained. Redistillation yielded ethyl $\beta\delta$ -dimethylpentane- $\beta\delta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (VI, R=Et) as a thick pale yellow oil, b.p. 153-155°/2 mm.; n_D^{20} , 1.4525. (Found: C, 60.74; H, 8.74. $C_{16}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 60.8; H, 8.86 per cent).

Cyclisation of VI (R=Et) to (VII).—The method and results are identical with those of Bardhan and Ganguly (*loc. cit.*).

Hydrolysis and Decarboxylation of (VII) to (III).—Results are identical with those of Bardhan and Ganguly except for the figure for m.p. of the semicarbazone of isofenchocamphononic acid. It (prisms from water) melted at 212-13° (decomp.) and at 218° in a bath previously heated to 210°. (Aschan gives 216-217° and 221° respectively).

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